

*Post-release monitoring of the
biocontrol agent “Trichilogaster
acaciaelongifoliae” for the control of
the invasive “Acacia longifolia” in
Portugal*

SEVENTH REPORT - 2023

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Technical team

Elizabete Marchante^{1*}

Francisco Alejandro López-Núñez^{1,2}

Liliana Neto Duarte^{1,2}

Hélia Marchante^{2*}

¹ Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal.

² CERNAS (Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal.

*Main contacts: emarchante@uc.pt | hmarchante@esac.pt

Introduction

This is the seventh report on the post-release monitoring of the biological control (hereafter biocontrol) agent *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* (Froggatt) for managing the invasive plant *Acacia longifolia* (Andrews) Willd. (Figure 1) in Portugal. Similar to previous reports, this is intended for submission to the competent authorities, namely the Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas (ICNF) and the Direção Geral de Alimentação e Veterinária (DGAV), in Portugal, as well as the Standing Committee on Plant Health of the European Commission. In contrast to the previous reports, this one covers a period of two years, specifically 2022 and 2023, due to funding limitations that prevented annual reporting. As detailed below, taking into account not only the optimization of effort and resources, but also the significantly expanded distribution of the biocontrol agent (hereafter BCA) by now, the monitoring approach has been modified.

The target-plant: *Acacia longifolia*

Acacia longifolia, an Australian species, is invasive in Portugal (is included in the National List of Invasive Species, Decreto-Lei n.º 92/2019, Presidência do Conselho de Ministros, 2019) and stands out as one of the most widespread invasive plants in coastal areas of the mainland. It causes significant adverse impacts on biodiversity and ecosystems (Marchante et al., 2008b, 2008a; Rascher et al., 2011, 2012; Marchante et al., 2015; López-Núñez et al., 2017; see Figure 2, bottom images), which persist over time and make restoration of invaded areas increasingly more difficult and complex (Le Maitre et al., 2011; Marchante et al., 2009, 2011a). Additionally, it diminishes forest productivity, particularly in littoral pine plantations, and increases the risk of wildfires (Le Maitre et al., 2011), resulting in negative socio-economic impacts. Control methods in use until recently (i.e., mechanical and/or chemical methods) have proven to be very expensive and often unsuccessful, primarily due to the extensive, persistent and long-lived seed bank accumulated in the soil (Marchante et al., 2010), that promotes the rapid reinvasion of cleared areas (Duarte et al., 2023; Marchante et al., 2011a). Therefore, biocontrol was considered to complement these methods.

Figure 1. *Acacia longifolia*, from left: plant, inflorescence, seeds in pods, and galls promoted by *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae*.

Figure 2. Coastal areas with native vegetation (top images) and areas densely invaded by *Acacia longifolia* (bottom images). The invasive plant has replaced the diverse native communities, comprising many shrubs and herbaceous species, with almost monospecific woody stands.

The biological control agent: *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae*

After more than 12 years of host specificity testing, risk assessment and permits (Jeger et al., 2016; Marchante et al., 2011b; Shaw et al., 2016), in November 2015, the BCA *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* (Australian bud-galling wasp) started to be released in pre-selected sites along the Portuguese coast (Marchante et al., 2017). This BCA is a highly host-specific organism, affecting almost exclusively *A. longifolia* and primarily targeting seed reduction, although it also decreases plant growth and vigour (Dennill, 1985; Dennill and Donnelly, 1991). It is a small Australian gall former (*Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae*, ca. 3 mm), with an annual life cycle, on average. During most of the year, it develops inside the galls (Figure 3). Emerging females actively search for flower buds, preferably, but also for vegetative ones, to oviposit eggs, and typically die after 2-3 days (Noble, 1940). As a result, galls are produced instead of flowers or new branches preventing seed production or vegetative growth, respectively. In the short-term, this leads to a reduction in seed production (and subsequent dispersal) and plant growth. In the longer-term, a decrease of germination is expected after control, fire, or other disturbances, as the soil seed bank receives fewer seeds each year. Additionally, less vegetative growth and physiological stress for the plants may also be expected, as they have to cope with heavy gall loads (Dennill, 1985). *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* has been successfully used for the control of *A. longifolia* in South Africa since 1982, significantly reducing both seed production and vegetative growth (Dennill and Donnelly, 1991; Impson et al., 2023; Wilson et al., 2011).

Figure 3. The biocontrol agent *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae*. From left: adult female; female ready to emerge from the gall and pupae remaining's; and galls promoted by *T. acaciaelongifoliae* with emergence holes.

Establishment and early effects of the BCA in Portugal (2015 – 2021)

In Portugal, *T. acaciaelongifoliae* was released mostly along the Portuguese coast, from 2015 to 2021, in many locations (Table 1, Figure 4). Following the initial release in nine sites in 2015, 66¹ galls were detected in five² of the release sites during the Spring and Summer of **2016** (Marchante et al., 2016; H. Marchante et al., 2017). In the subsequent year, **2017**, approximately 1100 galls were detected in the same five sites³ (E. Marchante et al., 2017). Throughout **2018** the monitoring effort detected almost 25000 galls in five sites, but while four sites remained consistent with previous years, one was new, as a site with establishment in 2016 was affected by a fire in October 2017, resulting in the loss of that population (Marchante et al., 2018). By **2019**, the establishment of the BCA was already observed in 33 sites⁴ along most of the Portuguese coast, from Riba de Âncora in the north to Faro in the south (Marchante et al., 2019). Subsequently, in **2020** and **2021**, the number of establishment sites had increased to at least 40 and 48, respectively, and it was no longer possible to count all the galls, as they were hugely numerous (Marchante et al., 2020, 2021; Figure 4).

¹ In the first report, 56 galls were mistakenly reported due to a summing error (all galls were correctly identified in each release site, but there was a mistake in the sum formula).

² In the first report, galls were reported in four sites, but later in the season, after the report submission, one gall was detected in Reserva Natural das Dunas de São Jacinto, bringing the total number of sites with establishment to five.

³ In the second report, galls were reported in five sites, but, later on, a few galls were detected in Coimbra, in a new site (Patos), increasing the number of sites with *T. acaciaelongifoliae* to six. However, due to a fire in October 2017, one site (Perímetro Florestal das Dunas de Cantanhede) was lost, leaving five sites with establishment.

⁴ In the 2019 report, 32 sites with establishment were reported, but, in June 2020, a new site was detected, most likely resulting from the 2018 release campaign, increasing the total number of sites with establishment in 2019 to 33.

Table 1. Number of release sites and sites with establishment of *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* in Portugal from 2015 to 2021.

Year	Number of release sites	Number of sites with establishment
2015	9	-
2016	19	5
2017	17	5
2018	33	5
2019	2	33
2020	19	40
2021	42	48

Figure 4. Sites where the biocontrol agent *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* was released and establishment confirmed (depicted by full dots) along the Portuguese coast from 2015 to 2021.

It is noteworthy that, in contrast to the initial years (2015–2018) when the number of sites with establishment was generally low (and number of galls in each site was typically low, in the order of hundreds or few thousands), there was a marked increase in establishment across numerous sites from 2019 onward.

This difference can be attributed to the release of wasps of South African origin until 2017 and thus not synchronized with the season and phenology of *A. longifolia* in Portugal. Since 2018, releases have involved wasps from Portuguese populations, resulting in better synchronization with the phenology of the host plant (*A. longifolia*) and more suitable meteorological conditions. Furthermore, when wasps spread naturally or when galls are redistributed instead of wasps, the wasps have a longer lifespan, as they emerge in the field rather than in a laboratory. This distinction is crucial, given their relatively short adult lifespan (averaging 2-3 days), and can also influence the level of establishment.

In 2019-2020, a more detailed assessment made at three sites with establishment since 2016 (Mata Nacional das Dunas de Quiaios, Reserva Natural das Dunas de São Jacinto and Mata Nacional de Leiria) revealed significant impacts on the reproductive output and vegetative growth of *A. longifolia* (López-Núñez et al., 2021). In plants of *A. longifolia* with galls, branches produced significantly fewer pods (-84.1%), seeds (-95.2%) and secondary branches (-33.3%) and showed some tendency to produce fewer phyllodes and increase growth of the main branch compared to branches with galls. Results further suggest that the effects of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* are not limited to branches with galls but are reflected at the tree level. This could be expected, since the formation of galls represents an energy expenditure for the entire plant and not only for the branches where galls develop (López-Núñez et al., 2021). These measured effects are noticeable when looking at plants more broadly, with some *A. longifolia* almost not producing flowers since 2020.

Although it is very important to evaluate the effects of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* from the beginning of the biocontrol establishment, it must be kept in mind that the number of plants with galls and the quantity of galls in each plant are still small and sparse compared to the numbers of available floral and vegetative buds of *A. longifolia* in very extensive invaded areas. Consequently, the effects detected are expected to be still indicative at this stage.

Post-release monitoring campaign in 2023

As in previous campaigns, the monitoring efforts were carried out primarily by the responsible team, from the Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Universidade de Coimbra (DCV/UC) and from the Escola Superior Agrária, Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra (ESAC/IPC). The team collaborated with technicians from ICNF, municipalities, NGOs, and forest companies in a strategic partnership aimed at involving various stakeholders. Additionally, since 2020, a citizen science project has been implemented to engage citizens in the monitoring of the BCA, while simultaneously increasing awareness of biocontrol (Marchante et al., 2024). This project includes two forms of reporting the presence of the BCA: i) a more detailed project in the App Epicollect5,

"Registo de *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae*"⁵; and ii) a simpler project in the App iNaturalist/BioDiversity4All, "*Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* in Iberian Peninsula"⁶. Regarding DCV/UC and ESAC/IPC, their involvement occurred within the framework of an ongoing project titled "Projeto Piloto 9 - Plantas invasoras", which was part of the larger project "F4F - Forest for Future, Reforço da capacitação de atores e redes de promoção de ações de desenvolvimento (Centro-08-5864-FSE-000031)", funded by Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and the European Union, through the European Social Fund. **This project focused on empowering stakeholders in the centre of Portugal, involving training and engaging technicians from various entities and citizens in the monitoring of the BCA, albeit with only a small task of fieldwork with the research team. Consequently, monitoring had to be reduced compared to initial years, leading to the production of this bi-annual report. This project is now concluded. Regrettably, funding for the next campaigns has not yet been secured, which means this may once again be jeopardized or greatly reduced in scope. It should be emphasized that this is a nationwide project with a clear applied focus and tangible results on the ground, providing benefits for conservation and the economy. Therefore, it shouldn't solely rely on academia for support. National nature conservation and environmental organizations should actively support or at least contribute funding to ensure that the crucial monitoring can continue.**

Given the *T. acaciaelongifoliae*'s widespread dispersal and establishment, the team responsible for this report has no longer released it in 2022 and 2023. However, over the course of the project, scientific and awareness activities have raised awareness, leading several land owners/ managers to express interest in releasing the BCA on their sites. Consequently, as in previous years, the BCA was intentionally released on some sites in 2022 and 2023. Site owners/managers were instructed to document release sites to assist the research team in monitoring the establishment and spread of the BCA. Unfortunately, complete reporting of the sites and numbers of galls or wasps has not always been provided. Additionally, the conspicuous nature of the galls allows citizens to pick them up and release them elsewhere without the team's knowledge. While the natural dispersal of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* could be expected to gradually colonize all sites where *A. longifolia* is present in the coming years, intentional releases have likely accelerated the rate of establishment. In light of these complexities, starting from this report, it was decided not to disclose specific release sites. This decision is motivated by the likelihood that the available information might be incomplete, and also because often it cannot be ascertained if the BCA reach the sites independently or with human assistance. Consequently, reporting release sites could lead to misleading or erroneous interpretations.

New monitoring methodology

Considering the current widespread distribution of *T. acaciaelongifoliae*, a new systematic methodology was implemented. This approach aims to complement the valuable yet incomplete and non-systematic citizen

⁵ Available at <https://five.epicollect.net/project/registo-de-trichilogaster-acaciaelongifoliae>

⁶ Available at <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/trichilogaster-acaciaelongifoliae-in-iberian-peninsula>

science records and to facilitate a comparison of the distribution and overall impact of the BCA over time. The new approach is grounded in a UTM grid spanning 10 x 10 km, allowing for relatively brief observational periods. To facilitate this, the existing Epicollect5 project was adapted to integrate information concerning the distribution (presence/absence), direct impacts on *A. longifolia* (efficacy) and non-target effects of the BCA (to evaluate specificity). With this updated methodology, we expect primarily to: 1) Assess the distribution of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* across the entire distribution area of *A. longifolia*; 2) Evaluate the effects of the BCA on *A. longifolia* seed production; and 3) Monitor direct effects on non-target species.

For this monitoring, two datasets were used: i) *Acacia longifolia* presence data obtained from GBIF and INVASORAS.PT platform; and ii) *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* presence data, using data from our release and monitoring database (E. Marchante et al., 2017; Marchante et al., 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2016), as well as data downloaded from GBIF and the citizen science projects mentioned above. The records were filtered and subsequently overlaid with a 10 x 10 km grid. Based on the analysis of this overlap, it was decided to confine the sampling area to a coastal strip of approximately 30 km, since over 90% of *A. longifolia* occurrences are concentrated in this region. Out of a total of 326 10 x 10 km grids, 204 were prioritized for sampling based on previous *A. longifolia* and/or *T. acaciaelongifoliae* presence data. The remaining grids were not sampled at this stage. Given the impossibility of sampling the entirety of each grid, specific sites were selected to monitor in the following order of priority: i) specific sites where the BCA was released, ii) sites with presence of BCA, or iii) in the absence of BCA records, sites with presence of *A. longifolia*. Efforts were made to ensure that the selected site was representative of the species distribution in the grid. At each selected site, whenever possible⁷, five locations were sampled - one central and four additional in the four cardinal directions, separated from the central location by a minimum of 100 m (indicative distance). At each of the five points, using the aforementioned Epicollect5 project, information was collected on location (coordinates), habitat type, species, and, in the case of *A. longifolia*, population size, plant size, presence of BCA galls, characterization of these when present, and the canopy cover of phyllodes, flowers, pods, and BCA galls. The cover was recorded using the scale: 0%, 1%-10%, 10%-25%, 25%-50%, 50%-75%, 75%-90%, >90%. Additionally, photos of the location were taken. At each site, the presence/absence of the BCA in other non-target plant species was also documented.

Since one of the main aims of the annual sampling is to assess the effects of the BCA on the target species, a sampling period coinciding with the peak fruiting of *A. longifolia* was established, from June 1 to July 30, 2023, allowing to additionally evaluate pod production. To streamline fieldwork and increase awareness about the importance of this monitoring, technicians from some entities (e.g., ICNF, municipalities, forest companies or NGOs) and citizens previously involved in the project were asked to sample selected grids.

⁷ Sometimes, a sufficient number of *A. longifolia* plants were not found at the sampling site to record all five points.

Based on the field collected data, several maps were generated, outlining the distribution and impacts of the BCA. The three most relevant were selected for this report: one displaying the presence/ absence of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* galls (Figure 5), and two others focused on the grids with presence of the BCA, showing for each grid the average cover of BCA galls (Figure 6a) and *A. longifolia* pods (Figure 6b). For simplicity, for the latter two, the coverage classes used were reduced to four: 0%, 1%-25%, 25%-75% and >75%. The data and scripts used to analyze and create these maps are available upon request in the Github repositior⁸.

Establishment of the BCA

Of the grids prioritized for monitoring (204), it was not possible to visit 10 grids (due to access limitations), nine in the coastal area and one more inland, with half of them having previous records of establishment of the BCA (Figure 5). From the 194 sampled grids, galls were observed in 109 of them, while in the remaining grids, it was not possible to observe galls of the BCA. Besides the coastal grids, 10 additional grids, in more inland locations, were sampled due to previous records of *A. longifolia*, with galls present in six of them.

Figure 5. Map depicting the presence or absence of *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* across coastal Portugal in 2023, using a 10 x 10 km grid. Except for 10 inland grids, sampled grids were located on costal areas with confirmed presence of *Acacia longifolia* and/or *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae*.

⁸ Available at https://github.com/Infran85/Trichilogaster_Monitoring.git

The BCA was most frequently recorded in the central coastal region of the country, followed by the north and northwest. Conversely, fewer records of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* establishment were noted in the southern region, particularly in the Cape St. Vincent area, and in the metropolitan area of Lisbon. This disparity could be attributed to less intense BCA releases or insufficient time for natural spread in these regions. A total of 1075 individuals/spots of *A. longifolia*⁹ were monitored in the 204 (194 coastal locations and 10 more inland) grid squares of 10 x 10 km. Of these, approximately half (532) had galls of *T. acaciaelongifoliae*.

Effect of the BCA on *Acacia longifolia*

Regarding the impact of the BCA on *A. longifolia*, in the majority of grids with confirmed BCA presence (62%), gall coverage on the *A. longifolia* canopy ranged between 1% and 25%; in close to one third of cases (34%), gall cover ranged between 25% and 75%, and in 4%, galls covered nearly the entire canopy (>75%; Figure 6a). When observing *A. longifolia* affected by the BCA, in the majority of monitored grid squares (57%), *A. longifolia* produced few pods (1 to 25% of the canopy covered by pods). In 10% of cases, more pods were produced, with a coverage ranging between 25% and 75% of the canopy, while only a third produced a large quantity of pods, covering nearly the entire canopy (Figure 6b). Despite the significant variability in the collected data, a small negative correlation was observed between the cover of BCA galls and the *A. longifolia* pod cover (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Map depicting the average percentages of *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* gall coverage (a) and *Acacia longifolia* pods (b) within the canopy of monitored *A. longifolia* trees with BCA presence in 2023.

⁹ Sometimes plants are intermingled and is difficult to separate them; in such cases, the spot was monitored.

Figure 7. Pearson correlation between the cover of *Acacia longifolia* pods and *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* galls.

Effects of the BCA on non-target plant species

As previously, observations were conducted to detect galls of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* on numerous non-target plants located in the vicinity of *A. longifolia* trees where the BCA was established. A total of 380 individuals from 76 plant species were monitored and, consistent with expectations (Marchante et al., 2011b), no BCA galls were observed on any of the species surveyed (see Table 2). These observations specifically included *Cytisus striatus* (giesta-das-serras) and *Acacia retinodes*, the former due to the detection of eggs on its buds in quarantine specificity tests, while the latter because it is valued commercially in Italy.

Table 2. List of non-target plant species surveyed in 2023 to detect galls of *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae*, ordered first by the most observed species and then alphabetically.

Species	Number observed	% observed	Number of BCA galls
<i>Ulex</i> sp.	96	25.3	0
<i>Acacia melanoxylon</i>	47	12.4	0
<i>Acacia saligna</i>	23	6.1	0
<i>Cistus salviifolius</i>	23	6.1	0
<i>Cytisus</i> sp. (<i>C. striatus</i> ou <i>C. grandiflorus</i>)	17	4.5	0
<i>Acacia dealbata</i>	14	3.7	0
<i>Stauracanthus</i> sp.	12	3.2	0
<i>Salix</i> sp.	9	2.4	0
<i>Rubus</i> sp.	8	2.1	0
<i>Ononis</i> sp.	6	1.6	0
<i>Quercus suber</i>	6	1.6	0
<i>Acacia retinodes</i>	4	1.1	0

Species	Number observed	% observed	Number of BCA galls
<i>Adenocarpus complicatus</i>	4	1.1	0
<i>Dittrichia viscosa</i>	4	1.1	0
<i>Eucalyptus</i> sp.	4	1.1	0
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	4	1.1	0
<i>Genista</i> sp.	4	1.1	0
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	4	1.1	0
<i>Olea europaea</i>	4	1.1	0
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	4	1.1	0
<i>Quercus faginea</i>	4	1.1	0
<i>Acacia pycnantha</i>	3	0.8	0
<i>Alnus lusitanica</i>	3	0.8	0
<i>Carpobrotus</i> sp.	3	0.8	0
<i>Cortaderia selloana</i>	3	0.8	0
<i>Erica</i> sp.	3	0.8	0
<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i>	3	0.8	0
<i>Quercus robur</i>	3	0.8	0
<i>Seseli tortuosum</i>	3	0.8	0
<i>Vitis</i> sp.	3	0.8	0
<i>Cistus ladanifer</i>	2	0.5	0
<i>Laurus nobilis</i>	2	0.5	0
<i>Lotus</i> sp.	2	0.5	0
<i>Nerium oleander</i>	2	0.5	0
<i>Osyris alba</i>	2	0.5	0
<i>Quercus coccifera</i>	2	0.5	0
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Arbutus unedo</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Artemisia campestris</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Asparagus</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Atriplex halimus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Avena</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Ceratonia siliqua</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Corema album</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Cotoneaster</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Daucus</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Ficus carica</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Halimium calycinum</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Ipomoea indica</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Lagurus ovatus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Lavandula stoechas</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Limoniastrum monopetalum</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Ononis ramosissima</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Paraserianthes lophanta</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Phillyrea angustifolia</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	1	0.3	0

Species	Number observed	% observed	Number of BCA galls
<i>Punica granatum</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Pyracantha</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Retama</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Rosa</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Rubia peregrina</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Ruscus aculeatus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Salpichroa origanifolia</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Santolina impressa</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Schinus molle</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Solanum</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Tilia</i> sp.	1	0.3	0
<i>Tropaeolum majus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Ulex argenteus</i> subsp. <i>argenteus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Viburnum tinus</i>	1	0.3	0
<i>Zea mays</i>	1	0.3	0
Total	380	100	0

Discussion

Establishment of the BCA

After eight years since the initial release of *T. acaciaelongifoliae*, with over 800 km covered and more than 200 grids surveyed in 2023, the establishment of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* along the Portuguese coast is evidently confirmed. The current methodology has allowed for the mapping and updating of the distribution of this BCA in Portugal, establishing a baseline for future comparisons.

The BCA is now distributed throughout the entire Portuguese coast from north to south, with a higher concentration observed in the northern and central regions. This distribution is influenced by several factors, notably a greater number of releases in these regions (López-Núñez et al., 2021), as well as a higher presence of *A. longifolia* for the BCA to establish. Once established, thanks to its dispersal capacity, aided by air currents, the BCA can spread widely from release points (Dennill, 1987; McGeoch and Wossler, 2000), most of which are located within the first 30 km of the coastline, colonizing new areas invaded with *A. longifolia*. It's important to note that potential releases of the BCA may have occurred unbeknownst to us, along with landscape-modifying interventions (e.g., vegetation clearance, including *A. longifolia*, fires, land use changes, etc.), impacting the current distribution of the BCA beyond its natural dispersion. Lastly, it's important to stress that this systematic sampling was based on the random selection of a representative *A. longifolia* point within the grid square. As such, the non-detection of the BCA at the monitored point does not exclude the possibility of its presence elsewhere within the grid square, indicating that these data may be incomplete. Additionally,

due to the inability to survey all the country, it's possible that the BCA is present in unsurveyed areas and has not yet been detected. Remote sensing techniques started to be explored to detect the BCA which can become a valuable additional source of information. Yet, funding is not yet secured to explore further this possibility. The BCA is spreading farther from release sites, sometimes within a few kms, decreasing detectability chances, as we don't know where it's spreading to. In addition to the rise in numbers of sites with establishment, the size of colonized areas is also expanding, with *T. acaciaelongifoliae* venturing into new areas, sometimes several hundred meters or even a few kms away (up to 7 km) from the focal trees where the wasps were initially released.

Despite synchronizing its life cycle with the Northern Hemisphere and now taking around one year to complete it, with a peak for emergency in May – June, significant variation in gall and site phenology was observed in 2023 (as observed previously and similar to South Africa), raising doubts about the number of generations per year. Although the BCA's life cycle was monitored in detail (Nunes et al., *under review*), the possibility of more than one generation per year couldn't be ruled out. As in previous years, most observed galls originated from flower buds, though some originated from vegetative buds (Nunes et al., *under review*).

Figure 8. Galls of *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* detected during post-release monitoring campaigns. Top, branches heavily colonized. Bottom, from left: flower and vegetative galls.

Effects of the BCA

Gall counting is now impractical, but in most sites where establishment occurred in previous years, it's evident that gall numbers continue to increase exponentially. During the *A. longifolia* flowering season, many plants exhibit minimal flowering as flowers are replaced by galls induced by the BCA. These effects are reflected in the assessments conducted in 2019-2020 (see above), which showed a clear local-level effect of the BCA on *A. longifolia*, reducing seed production and vegetative growth (López-Núñez et al., 2021). Such outcome was anticipated, given that each BCA female wasp can lay approximately 300 eggs on average, resulting in rapid population growth when synchronized with *A. longifolia*'s phenology in the Northern Hemisphere. These assessments were conducted at a microscale, posing challenges in extrapolating BCA effects to the landscape level. Through current national-level monitoring efforts, we have endeavored to evaluate the broader impacts of the BCA, albeit with a reduced level of detail. The results indicate that despite the widespread distribution of the BCA, its densities are often very low, especially in recently established populations. Notably, grid squares with higher gall densities typically coincide with locations where the BCA was released more than five years ago. In such cases, the gall density was higher, sometimes covering more than 75% of the canopy of *A. longifolia*. The BCA primarily induces galls on floral buds, thereby reducing the formation of inflorescences and, consequently, pods and seeds. Thus, although the observed correlation was modest, an increase in gall coverage is anticipated to correspond to a decline in pod production, as observed.

Conclusions

Overall, the BCA *Trichilogaster acaciaelongifoliae* has established along most of the Portuguese Coast and in some inland sites, **with a greater abundance observed in the northern and central regions**. The implementation of the new methodology has established a nationwide baseline for the BCA distribution, facilitating future comparisons. The BCA is establishing and spreading autonomously in Portugal, with galls observed several kilometres from the release sites in some locations. While the number of plants with galls and the quantity of galls per plant remain relatively low compared to the high abundance of *A. longifolia* floral and vegetative buds in extensively invaded areas, **it is notable that some sites already exhibit a high number of galls per plant and site. This is reducing significantly seed production in colonized plants, thereby diminishing the reproductive ability of *A. longifolia* and subsequently its invasive potential**. Additionally, plant growth is also being reduced. As time goes by, the impacts of the BCA are expected to continue to increase.

Monitoring of the establishment of *T. acaciaelongifoliae* and its effects on *A. longifolia* will continue, albeit with a more limited scope and frequency. This endeavor relies on ESAC/IPC and DCV/UC commitment

and collaboration with technicians, managers at release sites, and citizen scientists across the country. However, while our team actively seeks new funding, **the absence of secured funding for ongoing campaigns raises concerns about continuity**. Yet, now more than ever, there is a pressing need for detailed monitoring to evaluate the effects of the BCA on the landscape and trophic levels and to enhance its successful integration with other control methods.

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